

Photochemical Oxidation of Leuco-Malachite Green by means of Uranyl Nitrate in Monochloroacetic Acid Solution.

By

JNANENDRA CHANDRA GHOSH AND JADULAL MUKHERJEE.

The photochemical oxidation of some leuco-bases has been recently studied from the standpoint of technical application in colour photography by Carroll (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **30**, 130). His paper may be referred to for previous work in this subject. Carroll finds that the photochemical oxidation of the leuco-bases offers little hope of utility as a photographic process but it may be followed by optical methods of analysis and is well adapted to study of photochemical catalysis.

In the present paper we have studied the photochemical oxidation of leuco malachite green by means of uranyl nitrate. The results obtained are important in the sense that certain very simple relations have been discovered between the intensity of illumination, the concentration of the photochemical oxidising agent, and the concentration of the acceptor leucobase.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Leucobase of malachite green was prepared by condensing dimethyl aniline and benzaldehyde in presence of zinc chloride (Fischer, *Annalen*, 1883, **217**, 260, 262). It was purified by several crystallisations. The purified base was dissolved in 10 per cent. aqueous solution of mono-chloroacetic acid. Mono-chloroacetic acid solution of the base if allowed to stand for a sufficient length of time becomes gradually coloured. Hence each solution

was used for two or three days after it had been prepared. Crystallised uranyl nitrate was dissolved in distilled water and used.

The source of light was a 100 c. p. Pointolite lamp, the strength of the current and voltage of which was maintained constant by means of a regulating resistance. A parallel beam of light was obtained by placing a lens at its focal distance from the point source. Monochromatic light filters as prescribed by Plotnikow (*"Lehrbuch der Photochemie"*, p. 56, Table 14) were used. The reaction cell was made by cutting out 1 cm. sq. surface from a piece of brass plate 1 cm. thick and 4 cm. sq. which was afterwards electroplated with gold. The solution was kept in the hollow space in this brass plate by means of two optically plane glass plates held fast to the metal plate by means of rubber garters. The reaction cell was placed inside a double walled metal box provided with windows on opposite sides. The metal box was hinged on vertical supports fixed into the observation table of a König Marten spectrophotometer, so that at the time of taking readings the box could be turned through 90° degrees and at that position one half of the slit of the spectrophotometer was illuminated by light passing through the glass plates alone and the other half by light passing through the glass plates and the solution. Through the annular space of the box, water from a thermostat was circulated by means of a pump worked by an electric motor. The temperature within the box was maintained constant within 0.1°C (see Fig. 1).

Spectrophotometer readings were taken with different concentrations of the dye in a given uranyl nitrate solution. By plotting those readings against the concentrations, standard curves were prepared from which concentration of the dye in an unknown solution can be obtained by intrapolation. It has been found that for different uranyl nitrate concentrations with the same concentration of the dye different readings were obtained. Hence three different standard curves were prepared, as shown in Fig. 2, (1) with M/2 uranyl nitrate, (2) M uranyl nitrate, (3) M/4 uranyl nitrate. The concentration of the dye formed during the progress of reaction was obtained by taking the readings at different intervals and calculating from the standard curve. The intensities of the incident light were measured by noting the deflections of a Moll galvanometer connected with a Moll thermopile placed in front of the reaction cell. The galvanometer and the thermopile were calibrated by a Hefner lamp which according to Gerlach, gives on a sq. cm. at a distance

Fig. 1.

A—the position of the reaction cell when it was exposed to the incident light.

B—when the reaction chamber was turned through 90° and spectro-photometer readings were taken.

s—the slit; *a*—the light filters; *c*—the reaction cell;

d—the glass plates; the blackened portion—the brass plate.

Fig. 2.

Concentration of the dye formed.

of one meter 900 ergs. of radiation. The amount of light absorbed was calculated from the value of extinction coefficient of uranyl nitrate measured with the spectrophotometer.

$$\text{Wave-length} = 440\mu\mu.$$

Reading of the spectro-photometer with water in the path of light.

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Reading of the spectro-photometer with M/2 uranyl nitrate in the path of light.

42.1

Length of the cell = 1 mm.

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{cd} \cdot \log \frac{\tan \alpha_1}{\tan \alpha_2} = 1.15.$$

The dark reaction.—The velocity of the dark reaction at temperatures below 40°C was found to be too small to be taken into account in studying the velocity and the mechanism of the photo-chemical reaction. No after effect could also be noticed.

Table 1 gives the data for the progress of a given reaction.

TABLE I.

Intensity of the incident light = 199 ergs per sq. cm. p. s. Wave-length of the incident radiation = 478-410 $\mu\mu$. (Dunkel Blau, Plotnikow, "Lehrbuch der Photochemie," p. 56, Table 14).

Temp. 32°C.

Curanyl nitrate = M/2		C _{kinco base} = M/20
t in minutes.	Conc. of the dye formed.	Rate per hour.
0	0	...
40	0.000046	...
70	0.000056	0.000020
100	0.000066	0.000020
160	0.000084	0.000018
220	0.000104	0.000020
280	0.000124	0.000020

Mean rate per hour = .000020.

In the above table it will be seen that in the first 40 minutes the reaction rate is distinctly greater than what it is afterwards. The same phenomenon of a period of acceleration has been found also in all the other experiments. This is probably due to the fact that the leucobase at the beginning of the experiment is oxidised by the oxygen dissolved in the solution, the molecules of uranyl nitrate acting as a photosensitiser for this oxidation by oxygen.

The reaction rate is zero molecular and is very slow. The reaction has been found to be zero molecular in all the experiments. In the subsequent tables only the reaction rate and the conditions under which they have been obtained will be given. Table II gives the reaction rate for various intensities of light.

TABLE II.

Temp. 32°C

Wave-length of the incident radiation = 478—410 $\mu\mu$

$C_{\text{uranyl nitrate}} = M/2$	$C_{\text{leuco base}} = M/20$
Reaction rate	Intensity of light (ergs).
0.000042	400
0.000020	199
0.000007	67
$C_{\text{uranyl nitrate}} = M/2$	$C_{\text{leuco base}} = M/10$
Reaction rate	Intensity of light (ergs).
0.000050	400
0.000026	199
0.000008	67

TABLE III.

Intensity of light = 400 ergs. per sq. cm. p. s.

Wave-length = 478-410 $\mu\mu$. Temp. 32°C. $C_{\text{uranyl nitrate}} = M/2$

Reaction rate 0.000050 0.000042 0.000024 0.000018

 $C_{\text{leuco base}}$ M/10 M/20 M/40 M/60Intensity of light=199 ergs. Wave-length=478-410 $\mu\mu$ $C_{\text{uranyl nitrate}} = M/2$

Reaction rate 0.000026 0.000020 0.000012

 $C_{\text{leuco base}}$ M/10 M/20 M/40

TABLE IV.

Intensity of light=400 egrs.

Wave-length=478-410 $\mu\mu$ $C_{\text{leuco base}} = M/20$

Temp. 32°C

Reaction rate 0.000042 0.000086 0.000020

 $C_{\text{uranyl nitrate}}$ M/2 M M/4*Discussion.*

In our reaction there are two substances which react together and bring about a photochemical change. Uranyl nitrate which is coloured yellow has got absorption band in the visible region, while the leuco-base solution which is perfectly colourless is not sensitive to radiation in the visible region. According to the newer theories of the mechanism of a photochemical reaction active molecules of the photoactive components are first produced by absorption of radiant energy. The concentration of the active molecules formed is given by the equation

$$\frac{1}{2} I_0 (1 - e^{-\epsilon c l}) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where I_0 is the intensity of the incident light, ϵ the molecule extinction coefficient, c the concentration of the photoactive molecule, l the thickness of the solution and k a constant.

The activated molecule has a certain average life period of excitation and if within this period it can collide with an acceptor molecule, chemical transformation may occur. The probability of collision within the life period of excitation (τ) will in the cases of solution increase as the osmotic pressure of the acceptor molecules in solution increases, until for a large concentration of the latter, all the activated molecules bring about chemical transformation by collision. The rate of chemical transformation for a constant rate of production of active molecules is given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = c \frac{\tau}{T + \tau} \quad \dots \text{Eq. 2}$$

(Carvo, *Zeit. Physik*, 1922, 10, 185 ; Turner, *Phys. Review*, 1924, 23, 466).

Now the time period t between two successive collisions between an active uranyl nitrate molecule and leucobase molecule will, on the assumption that the kinetic theory of gases can be extended to dilute solutions, be given by the expression,

$$T = \frac{1}{Aa^3p}$$

where $A = 266 \cdot 66 \sqrt{\frac{2\pi N}{k\theta}} \cdot \frac{m_1 + m_2}{m_1 - m_2}$ a constant,

a the distance between the centres of two reacting molecules on collision and p the pressure of acceptor molecules expressed in millimetres of mercury. It is obvious that in order that T should remain constant during the progress of reaction, p should be kept constant. In our experiments total change was very small compared with the initial concentration of the base and its concentration therefore remained practically constant. The complete equation in our case is

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = kI_0 \left[1 - e^{-\epsilon cl} \right] \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{Aa^3\tau p}} \quad \dots \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

For weak absorption of light Eq. (3) transforms into

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = kI_0(a-x) \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{Aa^2\tau p}} \quad \dots \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

If the change in a given reaction be very small compared with the initial concentration of the reacting substances Eq. (4) reduces itself to

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = kI_0 \cdot a \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{Aa^2\tau p}}$$

In our experiments the change in the concentration of uranyl nitrate during the course of the reaction was almost insignificant compared with the concentration of uranyl nitrate. Eq. (5) indicates that for a particular reaction where a and p are constant $\Delta x/\Delta t$ or the rate is also constant. The experimental results agree with this conclusion. Eq. (5) also shows that $\Delta x/\Delta t$ is directly proportional to each of the variable factors provided that p and one of the factors I_0 and a are constant. Our data agree with this conclusion. For constant rate of production of excited molecules, *i.e.*, for constant light intensity and given uranyl nitrate concentration, the equation is

$$\frac{dx}{dt} \text{ or rate} = k \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{Aa^2\tau p}}$$

$$\text{or } \frac{1}{\text{Rate}} = \frac{1}{k} + \frac{1}{Aa^2\tau p} \cdot \frac{1}{k}$$

Therefore $1/\text{Rate}$ plotted against $1/p$ should be a straight line. The intercept of the graph is obviously

$$\frac{1}{k} \text{ and the slope } \frac{1}{k} \cdot \frac{1}{Aa^2\tau}$$

$$\text{Therefore } \frac{\text{Intercept}}{\text{Slope}} = Aa^2\tau.$$

$$\text{Intercept} = .6 \text{ and slope} = 6.8 \times 10^4$$

$a=2 \times 10^{11}$. If $a = 3 \times 10^{-8}$ cm., τ becomes 4.9×10^{-11} sec.

Intercept = 1.2 and slope = 14×10^3 so that τ has the same value.

Temperature Coefficient of the Reaction.

It has been found that for an increase of 10°C from 22° to 32° the reaction rate remained practically the same. Hence so far as the temperature coefficient is concerned this reaction falls under the category of photochemical reactions having no temperature coefficient.

Application of Einstein's Law of Photochemical Equivalence.

As this reaction has no temperature coefficient, its reaction rate varying directly as the intensity of light and uranyl nitrate concentration it was thought that Einstein's Law might be obeyed in this case. But actual calculation shows that more than one quantum is necessary to transform one molecule of leucobase and so the efficiency is less than unity.

TABLE V.

Conc. of uranyl nitrate = $M/2$

Rate for $M/10$ conc. of leuco-base $\frac{50 \times 10^{-6}}{60 \times 60}$ gm. moles. per.
sec. per litre.

Incident light intensity = 400 ergs.

Percentage of absorbed by $M/2$ uranyl nitrate concentration 1 mm. thick for wave-length limits $470-410 \mu\mu = 13.5$. Hence quantity of light absorbed per sq. cm. of the reaction cell per sec.

$$= \frac{13.5}{100} \times 400 \text{ ergs.}$$

No. of quanta of incident blue light of average wave-length

$$440 \mu\mu = \frac{18.5}{100} \times 400 \times \frac{440 \times 10^{17}}{8.55 \times 10^{-17} \times 8 \times 10^{10}} = 11.7 \times 10^{11}.$$

No. of moles. transformed per sec. per 1 c.c. (for the depth was 1 mm.)

$$\frac{50 \times 10^{-8}}{60 \times 60} \times \frac{6.06 \times 10^{11}}{1000 \times 10} = 8.4 \times 10^{11}.$$

Therefore $\frac{\text{No. of quanta}}{\text{No. of moles}} = 14$ approximately.

This calculation is based on the statement due to Plotnikow that the filters used in this investigation transmitted mainly blue light and only a very negligible quantity of light of other wave-lengths. A thorough investigation to test the validity of this statement is now in progress. It is also intended to study the influence of pure monochromatic radiation obtained with the aid of a monochromator on this photosensitive system.

Effect of Different Wave-lengths on the Rate of Reaction.

By means of light filters (Plotnikow, *loc. cit.*) the action of the following monochromatic radiation was separately studied,—red 780-639 $\mu\mu$; yellow 640-574 $\mu\mu$; green 540-505 $\mu\mu$; light blue 494-458 $\mu\mu$; dark blue 478-410 $\mu\mu$. The region 478-410 $\mu\mu$ was the most efficient. All the experimental data above recorded have been taken with this spectral region. Light blue had also some effect but it was very small compared with that due to dark blue; effect of red radiation was very small whilst those of yellow and green nil.

It was thought that the dye after it has been formed might absorb radiation and accelerate further change, hence we should have auto-catalysis in white light. No such phenomenon has been observed. We also made one experiment in which after some dye has been formed by the action of dark blue light we changed the filters and red light was made to be incident upon it but no further reaction took place in a sufficient length of time. Hence light absorbed by the dye has no effect in the rate of change of the reaction.

Summary.

1. The oxidation of the leucobase of malachite green by means of uranyl nitrate is purely a photochemical phenomenon.

2. Spectral region 478-410 $\mu\mu$ is the most efficient radiation in bringing about the photochemical change.

3. The photochemical oxidation has got no temperature coefficient.

4. The reaction rate varies directly as the light intensity and as the concentration of uranyl nitrate.

5. The inverse of reaction rate plotted against the inverse of the concentration of leucobase is a straight line, as demanded by Cairo-Turner equation.

THE CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY.

Received April, 19, 1927.